

HFNMTC BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2018
RGN 20 MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING I

Marking scheme

Question One

Master Kingly Johnson, a 20-year-old male college student, had unprotected intercourse with a prostitute while he was on vacation. In 10 days he reported to the OPD with complains of experiencing pain and burning on urination and has a yellowish-white discharge from his penis. His laboratory result shows positive Gram stain for *N. gonorrhoeae*.

- a. State four (4) groups of individuals who are at higher risk of contracting sexually transmitted infections (STIs). 4 Marks
- b. What are the possible specific complications of untreated gonorrhea in men and in women (two (2) each) 4 Marks
- c. What will be your nursing management for Johnson under the following:
 - i. Psychological care? 6 Marks
 - ii. Education on prevention of STIs 4 marks
- d. State two antibiotic the prescriber is likely to order for the treatment of Johnson condition 2marks

Question Two

Mr. Bartholomew, 22 years old, has reported to the Emergency Unit with complaints of cough, while you are on duty.

- a. What history would you obtain from Mr. Bartholomew on his present illness? 8 marks
- b. Before you conduct physical examination on Mr. Bartholomew, what preparations would you make on the environment? 4 marks
- c. State Six (6) purposes of physical examination 6 marks
- d. State the locations of the following heart sounds S1 and S2 2 marks

Question Three

Agya Nimo 35 year old farmer was admitted with jaundice and general bodily weakness, a blood test confirmed hepatitis B viral infection.

- a. Enumerate four groups of people at risk of contracting hepatitis B infection. 4 marks
- b. State six (6) signs and symptoms the patient will presents apart from jaundice and bodily weakness. 3 marks
- c. What will be your nursing care for Agya Nimo 10 marks
- d. Mention three complications of viral hepatitis 3 marks

Question Four

Miss Angela Osei-Bonsu, 22 years has been admitted to the female medical ward with the diagnosis of cholera.

- a.
 - i. State the causative organism for cholera 1 mark
 - ii. State the mode of transmission of cholera 1 mark
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of cholera 5 marks
- c. State four (4) clinical features of cholera 4 marks
- d. Describe the management of Miss Osei-Bonsu under;
 - i. Prevention of spread of infection while at the ward 5 marks
 - ii. Observation 4 marks

NMTC, BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER 2016
(D18 & RGM13) HRGN 040 MEDICAL NURSING I

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
 - Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
 - Each question carries 20marks
 - Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

Mr. Kwaku Mahama 35 years old is admitted to the Cardiothoracic Unit of Boasiako's Memorial Hospital with fever and haemoptysis. He is diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis.

- a. Apart from fever and haemoptysis, state **Six (6)** other clinical features of pulmonary tuberculosis – 3 marks
- b. State nursing diagnosis for *each* of the following; - 2marks
 - i. cough
 - ii. fever
- c. How would you prepare Mr. Mahama for discharge - 7 marks
- d. What are the preventive measures for Pulmonary Tuberculosis - 6 marks
- e. Mention **four (4)** complications of Pulmonary Tuberculosis - 2 marks

Question Two

A 25 year old Richard Oteng has been admitted to the medical ward of Holy Family Hospital with complaints of fever and bitterness in the mouth. He is diagnosed with malaria.

- a. State **Six (6)** clinical features that would suggest that he has severe malaria apart from axillary temperature greater or equal to 37.5 degree celcius. - 3 marks
- b. Describe the life cycle of plasmodium falciparum under the following;
 - i. Hepatic stage - 5 marks
 - ii. Erythrocytic stage - 5 marks
- c. Richard has potential for fluid volume deficit related to frequent vomiting. State **three(3)** nursing interventions for him. - 3 marks
- d. State **four (4)** people at risk of severe malaria - 4 marks

Question Three

Mr. Bartholomew, 22 years old, has reported to the Emergency Unit with complaints of cough, while you are on duty.

- a. What history would you obtain from Mr. Bartholomew on his present illness? - 8 marks
- b. Before you conduct physical examination on Mr. Bartholomew, what preparations would you make on the environment? - 4marks
- c. State **Six (6)** purposes of physical examination - 6 marks
- d. State the locations of the following heart sounds **S1** and **S2** - 2 marks

Question Four

Madam Adwoa Bonsu, 47 year old is admitted with the complaint of severe diarrhoea and vomiting for 24 hours. She was on intake and output chart. Her weight on admission is 50kg and was diagnosed of severe dehydration with metabolic acidosis.

- a. List **FIVE (5)** reasons for calculating fluid intake and output - 5marks
- b. List **FIVE (5)** categories of patients who need intake and output chart as a routine nursing intervention - 5marks
- c. Apart from diarrhoea and vomiting list **THREE (3)** other causes of metabolic acidosis - 3marks
- d. What will be your nursing management of Madam Adwoa Bonsu with regard to the metabolic acidosis - 7marks

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HFNMTC- BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER 2017
RGN 19, (RGN213) MEDICAL NURSING I
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

Mr. Kwame Amponsah 35 years old is admitted to the Cardiothoracic Unit of Boateng's Memorial Hospital with night sweat, loss of weight and haemoptysis. He is diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis.

- a. Apart from night sweat, loss of weight and haemoptysis, state Six (6) other clinical features of pulmonary tuberculosis - 3 marks
- b. How would you prepare Mr. Amponsah for discharge - 7 marks
- c. What observation will you make on the patient while on admission? - 6 marks
- d. Mention four (4) complications of Pulmonary Tuberculosis - 4 marks

Question Two

Mr. Agyarko, 38 years old is admitted to the medical ward with hepatitis caused by hepatitis B virus.

- a. State SEVEN (7) signs and symptoms that Mr. Agyarko will present - 7marks
- b. Describe how you will manage the diet therapy of Mr. Agyarko - 9marks
- c. What specific education would you give on the prevention of the spread of the disease on the ward? - 4marks

Question Three

- a. State the causative organism for cholera - 1 mark
- b. State the mode of transmission of cholera - 1 mark
- c. Describe the pathophysiology of cholera - 9 marks
- d. State ~~NINE~~ (9) clinical features of cholera - 9 marks
- e. Describe the management of Miss Osei-Bonsu under;
 - i. Prevention of spread of infection while at the ward - 5 marks
 - ii. Observation - 4 marks

Question Four

Mr. Bartholomew, 22 years old, has reported to the Emergency Unit with complaints of cough, while you are on duty.

- a. What history would you obtain from Mr. Bartholomew on his present illness? - 8 marks
- b. Before you conduct physical examination on Mr. Bartholomew, what preparations would you make on the environment? - 4marks
- c. State Six (6) purposes of physical examination - 6 marks
- d. State the locations of the following heart sounds S1 and S2 - 2 markS

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HFNMTc BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-APRIL 2021

(RGN22) RGN 213 MEDICAL NURSING I.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOUR

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark.

Question One

Mrs. Elsie Tetteh, 22 years old, has reported to the Emergency Unit with complaints of cough, while you are on duty.

- What SIX (6) questions will you ask her to investigate her chief complaint? - 6 marks
- Before you conduct physical examination on Elsie, what preparations would you make on the environment? - 4 marks
- State Six (6) purposes of physical examination - 6 marks
- State the locations where these sounds can be heard. - 4 marks

Question Two

Mr. Asumah Cephas, 54 years has been admitted to the male medical ward of Obeng Health Institute with anasarca. Laboratory investigations such as 24-hour urine collection – which reveals significant (marked) proteinuria – confirms the physician's provisional diagnosis of Nephrotic Syndrome.

- State Four (4) other causes of oedema - 4 marks
- State Eight (8) other clinical manifestations of Cepha's might present with - 4 marks.
- Explain to a first-year student nurse why he has anasarca. - 4 marks
- State a nursing diagnosis with six (6) corresponding nursing interventions, for EACH of the following problems of the patient.
 - anasarca - 4 marks
 - Possible break in continuity of skin due to accumulation of fluid in the tissues - 4 marks

Question Three

- A 25-year-old Maxwell Afriyie Abina has been admitted to the Male Medical ward of Holy Family Hospital, Berekum with complaints of fever and profuse vomiting with decreased skin turgor and oliguria. He is diagnosed with severe malaria.
 - Describe the life cycle of P. Falciparum under the Erythrocytic stage - 4 marks
 - State a nursing diagnosis and three (3) corresponding nursing interventions for the problems below.
Fever; - 6 marks
- Miss Priscilla, 22 years has been admitted to the female medical ward with the diagnosis of cholera.
 - Describe the pathophysiology of cholera - 5 marks.
 - Describe the management of Miss Priscilla under.
Prevention of spread of infection while at the ward - 5 marks.

NMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER, 2015
RGN 14 MEDICAL NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

A 50 –year old farmer was admitted to the emergency ward with the diagnosis of tetanus

- a. Mention **eighth (8)** signs and symptoms of this condition - 8marks
- b. Mention **ten(10)** nursing management of this condition - 10marks
- c. Mention **two(2)** complications of tetanus - 2marks

Question Two

Mensah, a 60-year old patient reported to the medical ward with provisional diagnosis of osteoporosis

- a. In **four(4)** sentences explain osteoporosis to a colleague nurse - 3marks
- b. In not more than **twelve (12)** sentences explain the pathophysiology of osteoporosis - 4marks
- c. Mention **six (6)** signs and symptoms of this condition - 6marks
- d. Mention **seven (7)** nursing management of Mr. Mensah - 7marks

Question Three

a. Explain the following each in not more than **fifty words**

- i) Chronic prostatitis - 2marks
- i i) Prostatodynia - 2marks
- iii) Non-prostatitis - 2marks
- iv) Mention **six (6)** nursing observation you will make on this patient - 6marks

b. Mention **four (4)** important education you will give to a patient who is having prostatitis. - 4marks

c. State **four (4)** complications of prostatitis. - 4marks

Question Four

Mr. Baba a 40 -year old man reported to the medical ward with a provisional diagnosis of acute pancreatitis.

- a. How would you explain “acute pancreatitis” to a junior nurse in the ward - 3marks
- b. Mention **ten (10)** signs and symptoms of this condition - 5marks
- c. As a nurse on duty mention **five(5)** dietary management of Mr. Baba - 5marks
- d. State **three (3)** medical management of Mr. Baba - 3marks
- e. Mention **four(4)** risks factors that can bring about this condition - 4marks

NMTC, BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER 2015
(D17) HRGN 040 MEDICAL NURSING I
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Answer each question in a separate answer booklet
- All questions carry equal marks (20 marks Each)
- Carefully read questions and provide only relevant answers, no mark for irrelevant one
- Answers provided beyond the number specified attract no mark

Question One

A 25 year old Bernard Obeng has been admitted to the male medical ward of a Hospital with complaints of fever and bitterness in the mouth. He is diagnosed with uncomplicated malaria.

- a. State Six (6) clinical features that would suggest that he has severe malaria apart from axillary temperature greater or equal to 37.5 degree celcius - 3marks
- b. Describe the life cycle of plasmodium falciparum under the following;
- i. Hepatic stage - 5marks
 - ii. Erythrocytic stage - 5marks
- c. Bernard has potential for fluid volume deficit related to frequent vomiting. State three(3) nursing interventions for him. - 3marks
- d. State Four (4) people at risk of severe malaria - 4marks

Question Two

A 26 year old Mrs. Osei Gifty is admitted to the female medical ward of Holy Family Hospital, Techiman with Buruli ulcer. Her wound on the left knee requires daily dressing. As a student nurse on duty, you have been asked by the Ward In-charge to dress the wound.

- a. What objective data would you obtain from the affected part - 8marks
- b. How would you manage her under the following headings;
- i. Psychological care - 4marks
 - ii. Prevention of spread of infection while on the ward - 6marks
- c. Mention two complications she is likely to develop - 2marks

Question Three

All: nWadrego 51 year old is diagnosed of pulmonary tuberculosis on your ward. He is married and has three (3) children all of going age and lives in a chamber and a hall apartment with his family in a densely populated area.

- a. In not more than two sentences, describe the mode of transmission of Alhassan Wadrego's condition. - 2marks
- b. Enumerate TEN(10) signs and symptoms of Alhassan Wadrego condition - 5marks
- c. State two (2) specific diagnostic tests that should be done - 2marks
- d. Enumerates NINE (9) ways in which you will do to prevent the spread of Alhassan Wadrego's condition at home on his discharge. - 9marks
- e. State two (2) complications of his condition. - 2marks

Question Four

Adwoa Attaa 13 year old is brought to the hospital with a diagnosis of dehydration secondary to severe vomiting for more than 24 hours. The doctor has ordered an iv ringer lactase 2 litres for 24 hours.

- a. State only ten (10) other factors apart from vomiting that can upset electrolyte balance - 5marks
- b. State only six (6) clinical features that would alert you that the patient has metabolic acidosis. - 6marks

DakuraKumbio, aged 16 years has been admitted to the male medical ward in your hospital suffering from Cerebrospinal meningitis

- c. Enumerate FOUR causative organisms of this condition 2 marks
- d. Describe how you will prepare the patient for lumbar puncture 7 mar

NMTC, BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER 2015
(D17) HRGN 040 MEDICAL NURSING I
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Answer each question in a separate answer booklet
- All questions carry equal marks (20 marks Each)
- Carefully read questions and provide only relevant answers, no mark for irrelevant one
- Answers provided beyond the number specified attract no mark

Assessment

Question One

- Mr. Bartholomew, 22 years old, has reported to the Emergency Unit with complaints of cough, while you are on duty.
- What history would you obtain from Mr. Bartholomew on his present illness? - 8 marks
 - Before you conduct physical examination on Mr. Bartholomew, what preparations would you make on the environment? - 4 marks
 - State Six (6) purposes of physical examination - 6 marks
 - State the locations of the following heart sounds S1 and S2 - 2 marks

Diseases caused by insects and animals

Question Two

- A 25 year old Bernard Obeng has been admitted to the male medical ward of Holy Family Hospital with complaints of fever and bitterness in the mouth. He is diagnosed with uncomplicated malaria.
- State Six (6) clinical features that would suggest that he has severe malaria apart from axillary temperature greater or equal to 37.5 degree celcius - 3 marks
 - Describe the life cycle of plasmodium falciparum under the following;
 - Hepatic stage - 5 marks
 - Erythrocytic stage - 5 marks
 - Bernard has potential for fluid volume deficit related to frequent vomiting. State three nursing interventions for him. - 3 marks
 - State Four (4) people at risk of severe malaria - 4 marks

Food and water borne diseases

Question Three

- Miss Angela Osei-Bonsu, 22 years has been admitted to the female medical ward with the diagnosis of cholera.
- State the causative organism for cholera - 1 mark
 - State the mode of transmission of cholera - 1 mark
 - Describe the pathophysiology of cholera - 5 marks
 - State Six (6) clinical features of cholera - 6 marks
 - Describe the management of Miss Osei-Bonsu under;
 - Prevention of spread of infection while at the ward - 5 marks
 - Observation - 4 marks

Question Four

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION APRIL, 2021
RM 17 MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING I,
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

A 21-year-old student is admitted to the medical ward with the diagnosis of bronchial asthma. She complained of dyspnoea and was producing thick tenacious mucous. She looks anxious.

- a. Enumerate **FIVE (5)** precipitating factors of acute asthmatic attack. - 5marks
- b. Describe the nursing care you would render to the patient under:
 - i. Relief of dyspnoea - 6 marks
 - ii. Observation - 6 marks
- c. Enumerate six (6) precipitating causes of status asthmaticus - 3marks

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Atobrah, a 45-year-old unemployed was admitted to the male medical ward with a diagnosis of liver cirrhosis.

- a. List the **FOUR (4)** types of Liver Cirrhosis. - 2 marks
- b. State **TWELVE (12)** clinical manifestations that Mr. Atobrah is likely to exhibit. - 6 marks
- c. Describe the nursing management you would render to Mr. Atobrah under the following:
 - i. Skin care - 6 marks
 - ii. Nutrition - 6.marks

QUESTION THREE

Paul Atanga, a 21-year-old SHS graduate, is on admission at your ward with diagnosis of Acute Renal Failure (ARF) due to post renal factor.

- a. Mention **SIX** post-renal causes of Acute Renal Failure - 3marks
- b. Outline **TEN** clinical manifestations of ARF - 5marks
- c. Describe his nursing management under:
 - i. Observation - 6marks
 - ii. Diet - 4marks
- d. State **FOUR** complications of ARF - 2marks

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HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER-2017
RM 14, RMD214 MEDICAL NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 HOUR
OBJECTIVES

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
 - *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
 - *Each question carries 20marks*
 - *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

Master Awal, a young adult patient who has had repeated hospitalization for sickle cell crisis is on admission on your ward.

- a. Enumerate SIX (6) possible factors that might have precipitated Awal's repeated attack of sickle cell crisis - 3marks
- b. Describe your nursing interventions under the following headings
 - I. Pain relief - 6marks
 - II. Prevention of crisis - 8marks
- c. List SIX (6) complications of sickle cell disease - 3marks

Question Two

Nurse Dede a newly qualified nurse is to conduct physical examination on a 60-year old banker who came to the outpatient department for her regular medical examination.

- a. Enumerate the SIX (6) purpose for conducting physical examination - 3marks
- b. State SIX (6) guidelines nurse Dede need to follow in conducting the physical examination - 6marks
- c. Araba, 5 years old was rushed into the Paediatric emergency with complains of diarrhoea and vomiting. A diagnosis of severe dehydration was made. What will be your nursing management for Araba? - 7marks
- d. List four complications for severe dehydrations - 4marks

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HFNMTC -BEREKUM /ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2018

RM 15 RMD 214: MEDICAL NURSING I

TIME ALLOWED: 1 HRS.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

Mr. and Mrs. Ocansey had their wedding 4 months ago. The Hepatitis B Surface Antigen test of Mrs. Ocansey reveals positive, but that of the husband's status is unknown. However, the couple are desirous to have their own biological children.

- a. State FIVE (5) categories of people who are at risk of contracting Hepatitis B infection. - 5marks
- b. Mention EIGHT (8) clinical manifestations of Hepatitis B infection. - 4marks
- c. Describe your education under the following:
 - i. Sexual life of Mr. and Mrs. Ocansey - 4marks
 - ii. Prevention of spread of Hepatitis B in the community - 5marks
- d. Mention FOUR (4) complications of Hepatitis B infection - 2marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Ayishetu Seidu, a 55 year old is admitted to the ward with diagnosis of hypertension.

- a. Enumerate six possible causes of secondary hypertension - 3 marks
- b. State six specific investigations that can be carried out to identify the type of hypertension - 3marks
- c. What will be your nursing management of Madam Seidu under the following
 - I. Patient teaching / education - 8marks
 - II. Observation - 4 marks
- d. List four complications of hypertension - 2 marks